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Living labs: dealing with uncertainty in solving complex problems

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ABSTRACT

In engineering education students are increasingly challenged to solve complex socio-technological problems. However, there are many uncertainties in solving those 'ill-defined wicked problems'. For students, dealing with uncertainty is not easy to master.

In the minor and master programmes of Science Education and Communication at Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands, living Labs ('C-labs') are used to teach students to deal with real-life complex communication problems in technological innovation processes. Students collaborate in teams of four persons, all from different technological disciplines. Each team works closely with professionals who face the problem in practice. In the C-labs, design methodology is used to approach the problems in a structured way.

In this study we raise the question: how do students deal with uncertainties in solving complex problems in the C-labs? To answer this question we identified 3 sources of uncertainty: attributed to the individual, to the social context and to the task [7] and monitored the students during the design process by means of surveys and interviews.

Data analysis shows that students perceive all 3 kinds of uncertainty in the various stages of the design process. They use of a broad variety of responses to tackle uncertainty. The outcomes can be used to improve our ways to help students to deal with uncertainties.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Problem and research question

In a report about the global state-of-the-art in engineering education Ruth Graham [1] identifies a move towards “socially relevant and outward facing engineering curricula” (p. III) that are characterized by student choice, multidisciplinary learning, and societal impact. Graham emphasises the importance of opportunities for students to gain experience outside the classroom, outside traditional engineering disciplines, and in international contexts. Overall, she anticipates a more connected curriculum for engineering students, delivered through a connected spine of design projects [1]. This is best done in dedicated learning environments that bring together social relevance, technical innovation, entrepreneurship, multi-disciplinarity, and collaboration[1] [2].

In the Netherlands, several universities have created these environments in the form of innovation spaces or living labs. In these innovation spaces projects are executed by students, together with external parties. The involvement of businesses and government, users, citizens and/or communities set living lab settings apart from regular learning environments in project-based education. Traditional academic teaching and learning is challenged by the way learning is organised in living labs [3].

In the minor and master program of Science Education and Communication at Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands, living Labs (‘C-labs’) are used to teach students to deal with real-life, complex communication problems in technological innovation processes. Students from different technological disciplines work together in teams to solve a real-life problem. Each team collaborates closely with the professionals who face the problem in practice.

In the C-labs, design methodology is used to approach the complex innovation problems. Design is seen as a creative, disciplined, and decision-oriented inquiry, carried out in iterative cycles [4]. During the cycles a design solution is developed by repeatedly exploring organized knowledge, intuition, experience and creativity as well as testing alternative solutions. This dynamic process goes on until the students developed confidence in the viability of one of the solution alternatives [5].

A crucial skill in designing is a capacity to cope with uncertainty. In dealing with complex problems, ignoring or avoiding the uncertainty leads to superficial solutions to non-existing problems rather than to making a real positive impact [6]. However, the capacity of dealing with uncertainty is actually difficult to master [7].

In this study the question is raised how students deal with uncertainties in solving complex problems in the C-labs. We investigated which uncertainties students experience at which stage of the design process, and which mechanisms they currently use to tackle them. The results can be used to form ideas about how we can teach students effectively how to deal with uncertainties in this context.

1.2 Case study: C-lab courses

The concept of the C-labs is based on authentic learning and design-based learning (DBL). Authentic learning is learning by being involved in real-world problem solving [8]. DBL is described by Gomez Punte, van Eijck, & Jochems [9] as “an educational approach where students gather and apply theoretical knowledge to solve design problems” and rooted in “active learning methods that facilitate students’ learning

processes” (p.14). Designs can relate to products, tools, devices and strategies [9]. Basically, DBL is a teaching approach similar to, and often compared with, problem-based learning; however, in DBL the design process is pivotal.

Cases were submitted by government, industry and non-profit organizations. These clients were actively involved during the entire process, from problem definition to the presentation of the product. They were available for input and feedback; at set times and when students had specific questions.

Students worked in teams of 4 and each team focused on a different case; all complex socio-technical problems from practice. Criteria for group composition were students' fields, varying from computer science, mechanical engineering to architecture and industrial design; student preferences for a specific case; and scores on the DISC test for personality types (DISC stands for Dominance, Influence, Steadiness & Conscientiousness [10]).

The C-lab courses took one semester. Students worked on the case from day 1. The lectures and supervision by the teacher and student assistants were aimed at getting students to go through the design process in a systematic way, based on the double diamond model of the British Design Council [11], see figure 2.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Uncertainty

In this study the different types of uncertainty we discern between are derived from Daalhuizen et al. [7]. They mention that designers who work on innovations “have to deal with uncertainty associated with complexity, multi-disciplinarity and outcomes that in early phases are not – and are not supposed to be – foreseeable” (p.147). They stress that “design methodology aims to support the designer by providing structure and thus assist in dealing with uncertainty”, but in practice “design methodology often does not provide methodological support that is adaptable to the individual's needs in situations of unusual or high uncertainty”. They call these situations ‘non-routine’ situations, in which the designer does not know how to proceed.

“In routine situations, designers will either directly release a pre-set response, called skill-based behaviour. Or when features of a familiar situation are recognized, they make short-cuts within the model called rule-based behaviour (p.148-149). In non-routine situations designers go through several steps to make a decision and define a course of action. As a consequence of the frequent occurrence of non-routine situations in design processes, it is expected that the designer often performs on a knowledge-based level. In these situations, the designer will have to focus his attention on the situation and analyse and develop an understanding of the situation at an increasingly abstract level in order to develop an appropriate course of action” (see figure 1).

Fig. 1. Sources of uncertainty leading to non-routine situations and knowledge based action. Source: Daalhuizen et al. (2009), p 150.

Almost all students who participate in the C-labs have some experience with designing and design methodology; it is incorporated in their programmes. However, none of them have any experience in designing solutions to complex socio-technical problems. In comparison with the practitioners in the study of Daalhuizen et al. [7] the students have less routine in designing and dealing with uncertainties. Still, we think the model of Daalhuizen et al. is a good starting point in our study. Daalhuizen et al. describe three sources of uncertainty: uncertainty attributed to the individual, to the social context and to the task. We tuned these definitions of the sources of uncertainty to the situation in this case-study:

1. Uncertainty attributed to the individual is caused by the absence of having the required knowledge, rules or skills to proceed in a way that is appropriate for the problem at hand. In these situations, uncertainty is perceived to be associated with the person him/herself.
2. Uncertainty attributed to the social context is perceived to be associated with the interaction between the student or team of students with the commissioners. Issues as trust and shared understanding play a crucial role.
3. Uncertainty attributed to the task in the design process, is caused by a lack of understanding of the current status or the complexity of the task necessary to proceed in a way that is appropriate for the problem at hand. In these situations uncertainty is perceived to be associated with the task itself.

2.2 Design methodology

The Double Diamond model of the British Design Council (figure 2) was used to visualise the design process in the C-lab course. In this case-study we used this model to indicate at what moment in the design process uncertainties were perceived by the students and the lecturer. The model is divided into four distinct phases – Discover, Define, Develop and Deliver. These four stages were used to indicate at what moments which uncertainties were most present.

Starting point of the model is that in all creative processes a number of possible ideas are created (‘divergent thinking’) before refining and narrowing down to the best idea (‘convergent thinking’), and this can be represented by a diamond shape. But the Double Diamond indicates that this happens twice – once to confirm the

problem definition and once to create the solution. In order to discover which ideas are best, the creative process is iterative. This means that ideas are developed, tested and refined a number of times, with weak ideas dropped in the process. Practical design methods – like user diaries, journey mapping and character profiles – move a project through the four phases of the Double Diamond.

Fig. 2: The Double Diamond model of the British Design Council [10].

3 METHODOLOGY

In this study, we focus on one C-lab course in 2017-2018, attended by 36 students, who were divided into 9 teams. The students were monitored during the entire design project. *At the start* of the course they were asked to fill out a questionnaire individually, with open questions about their expectations of the course, their experience with designing, the challenges they were looking forward to and were fearing most, and their preferred way of working (with strict guidelines versus with a lot of autonomy). *During the course* they were asked every week to reflect on the past days and to note for every day what kind of activities they performed, what insights they obtained from the activities (both positive and negative), and how (un)certain they felt. They were asked to respectively visualise the activities, insights and uncertainties on three similar timelines, which made the connection between an activity, insight and uncertainty visible. *At the end of the C-lab* two students per team took part in semi-structured interviews. They were asked to consider the design process in retrospect, and share the insights they obtained during the course; the uncertainties they dealt with and the mechanisms they used to overcome the uncertainties.

Students participated on a voluntary basis. They all signed a consent form, stating that the researcher would carry out the research independently; answers would not be shared with the teacher of the C-lab, and results would be made anonymous. Students were asked to fill in the weekly surveys at set times when they worked independently on their case. They were free not to answer questions. In general, they were willing to participate in the research. However, in the final stage of their project, most students were less extensive in their answers than at the beginning. Each team decided in consultation which team members would participate in the interviews. Participants could sign up for a specific time slot in which the interview would be held. Generally they were open and answered questions in detail.

In the data-analyses the weekly surveys formed the starting point. First, it was decided which weeks corresponded with what phases of the design process

(discover, define, develop & deliver). The mentioned uncertainties per design phase were coded via open coding and divided into three categories: uncertainty attributed to the individual, the social context and the task. The 18 interviews with students were transcribed, and again, the uncertainties mentioned were coded. The ways students said to cope with the uncertainties were related to the types of uncertainties. The data from the surveys at the start of the course were used to see whether the expectations of individual students matched their experiences.

In a similar course in 2018, the lecturer was interviewed on a weekly basis. He was asked to reflect on the progress of teams, his perception of the uncertainty of the students in the particular stage of the design project and the way he anticipated and / or reacted on their uncertainty in his lectures and in his supervision. The interviews with the lecturer were transcribed and used to interpret the outcomes of the student-data of the course described in this case study. They were especially of help to interpret students' uncertainties related to the social context.

Below we present the results of the study per source of uncertainty.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Uncertainty attributed to the individual

Uncertainties attributed to the individual were not often mentioned in the weekly surveys, but were discussed in the surveys at the start of the project and in the interviews at the end. Some students indicated that thinking 'outside the box' was not one of their core competences, they were afraid not being creative enough. Others feared the converging phase: "making choices from endless possibilities". Various students indicated that they were unsure whether they could provide sufficient motivation for the project, given the iterating nature of the design process ("start over when reaching a dead end", or "go through to trial and error, over and over again"). A number of students were also uncertain about making decisions, but for another reason. They claimed to be perfectionists and found it difficult to decide 'when is something good enough'. Others indicated that they worked hard to achieve high marks in their study programmes. For them it was difficult if the lecturer did not indicate to what extent he agreed with the decisions made by the team, or if the client did not seem to understand the team's decisions.

Depending on the nature of the uncertainty, these 'individual' uncertainties related to a certain stage of the design process. In the interviews at the end of the project, some students indicated that their experience with this design process already made them feel less insecure. This was particularly the case with uncertainties about lack of creativity. Providing focus and staying motivated when iterations proved necessary were not mentioned in this context.

4.2 Uncertainties attributed to the social context

Analysis of uncertainties attributed to the social context revealed an interesting development, that was also recognised by the lecturer. At the start of the project (discover phase), most students felt insecure towards the client. They felt like having little control over the problem and thought the client would expect output in an early stage. In the next phase (define), students seemed to feel a little more secure about their own decisions, - they gained substantive and contextual knowledge - but were afraid that the client would not (fully) endorse their problem statement. In the third phase (develop) the uncertainty about the content was less prominent than in

previous phases; some students even indicated that they felt more like being an expert than the client, in certain respects. What they were uncertain about is how they should 'take along' the client in their decisions. In the final phase, most students were proud of the product of their design, but some felt uncertain about the appreciation of the client and the lecturer.

Patterns of uncertainty in the collaboration within the teams are much less clearly recognizable. Three students reported feeling insecure on the team. Two of them already indicated in the questionnaire before the start of the project that they were not looking forward to cooperating in a team for an entire semester. Most of students' reflection about team collaboration related to a specific situation ("preparing a presentation together went badly") and seemed to be rather insights about what went well or not in the collaboration than an indication of uncertainties.

Various students who indicated in the initial survey that they were anticipating problems in the diverging phase or students who had difficulty converging, indicated in the interviews that due to the cooperation in the teams, these potential shortcomings proved not to be a problem.

4.3 Uncertainties attributed to the task

Most of the uncertainties mentioned by the students in their weekly survey were uncertainties attributed to the task. Especially in the discover and define stage, many uncertainties were reported, due to the complexity of the task. Students did not know where to start, how to get grip on the problem. In retrospect however, students mentioned that they had gained a lot of insights in these first stages and learned quickly.

In every stage of the design project students were asked to apply particular tools, like a causal diagram, a theoretical framework or a customer journey. A lot of the uncertainties had to do with these methods: "What do we exactly have to do; How do we have to interpret the assignment; Are we on the right track?"

Another important source of uncertainty was (in the students' perception) 'the long absence' of feedback or getting negative feedback.

Each team had the feeling to be 'stuck' one or more times during the design process, which forced them to iterate and to revise their principles. These situations created uncertainty for many members of the teams. However, students who had indicated in the first survey to prefer to take a lot of their own initiative in the process, reported fewer uncertainties than other students. Most students were hesitant to actively approach the client, especially when they didn't have a well-defined question. Initially this also applied to approaching the lecturer, but to a lesser extent.

In the perception of the lecturer, student uncertainty especially arises during the transition from one phase in the design process to the other. In the analysis this was not quite visible, due to the fact that for every team the transition took place on another moment. However, during the interviews, this finding was confirmed by some students.

4.4 Copings mechanisms: responses to non-routine situations

What are the copings mechanisms reported by the students? Related to the task the most mentioned mechanisms were: to take ownership of the project (take initiative and rely on the intuition and expertise of the team members), dare to ask and to involve others, and especially: to keep going. Some students emphasized however,

that it helped them not to stick to the problem but to focus on something else for a while. Several students mentioned that using theory helped them to make decisions. The student interviews at the end of the project showed that their uncertainty with regard to the application of a certain tool diminished when it turned out that others in the team could handle the tool well: they learned from their team mates.

Related to the social context, students did not mention many coping mechanisms. Some mentioned that they would like to get some training in managing expectations of the clients, especially in the last two phases of the design process. The lecturer noted in an interview that the lack of prior knowledge about the context of a problem and the actors involved, makes students often ask very basic questions that often surprise clients in a positive way. Clients themselves are often so deeply involved that they find it difficult to approach a problem from a different perspective. The lecturer indicated that this aspect could be emphasized more in the living lab, in the hope of reducing uncertainty of students in the discover and define phase.

Students who struggled with uncertainties with regard to their position in the team and the collaboration with other students, did not come up with clear ideas for solutions or coping strategies. They responded moderately positive to the interviewer's suggestion that more attention to personal professional development in the living labs might help.

Regarding the individual uncertainties, some students who participated in the interviews indicated that keeping a log helped them to reflect and to see their uncertainties in proportion. In their opinion, addressing their uncertainties proved to be helpful. One student remarked that the survey at the start of the living lab made her aware of her uncertainties. She decided to formulate personal learning goals to overcome those.

5 CONCLUSION

The main question of this paper was: how students deal with uncertainties in solving complex problems in the C-labs?

Students identified uncertainties in the three categories of Daalhuizen et al. [7]. Especially in the discover and define phase, students experienced a lot of task-oriented uncertainties, which partly arose from the complexity of the problems. Context-related uncertainties with regard to the role of clients changed during the various phases of the design process. Some students also experienced uncertainties regarding their role and position in the team. Individual uncertainties are less tied to certain phases.

Students mentioned various coping mechanisms with regard to uncertainties attributed to the tasks: to take initiative and rely on the intuition and expertise of the team members, to dare to ask and to involve others, to keep going, or to focus on something else for a while. Several students noted that using theory helped them to make decisions. Only a few solutions were mentioned for handling individual uncertainties: keeping a log and addressing their uncertainties. Dealing with social uncertainties related to client expectations and participation in the team were issues that some students could not deal with properly.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Methodology

The methods used in this study: the distinction between the three types of uncertainty; the four design phases, and the fact that we have questioned students at different times and in different ways, has yielded a varied picture of the uncertainties that students experience. In this paper we have limited ourselves to giving global results, without going into detail, which we believe is most relevant in the context of the SEFI conference.

All reported uncertainties in this study could be categorized into the three types of uncertainty. However, it might be useful to add a fourth category 'technological uncertainties' in cases in which substantive knowledge of a technology is of great importance.

6.2 Lessons learned

In their paper Daalhuizen et al. [7] mention that "designers focus primarily on issues related to the task and to the social context" (p. 9-157). The authors stress that there is a need to encourage professional designers to reflect on their own contribution to non-routine situations.

In this study we learned that students within the C-lab were (still?) open to express their individual uncertainties. The lesson we take from this, is to pay attention to those individual uncertainties in an early stage: to address the individual uncertainties in engineering education and teach students how to reflect. This made us decide to add a module Personal Professional Development to our C-labs at Delft University of Technology.

In addition, we would like to add a masterclass about dealing with client expectations as well. After all, students were unable to indicate how they could deal with social uncertainties.

In the context of lifelong learning it could be valuable to include the uncertainties and copings mechanisms of clients and other stakeholders in our investigation into living labs as well: it could benefit cooperation between all parties in the living labs.

So, investigating our engineering education in detail offers us concrete starting points for improving education in living labs.

6.3 Relevance for Engineering Education

Until now, there has been little research into living labs. There is still much to discover. If we want to apply this type of education more frequently, we must ensure that sufficient attention is paid to students' uncertainties, in order to prepare future engineers better for the problems they will encounter in practice. Dealing with uncertainties is relevant for gaining adaptive expertise; a competence we will all need in our rapidly changing society.

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